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Searching for a viable approach to project work in engineering education

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ABSTRACT

Many engineering departments across the world are moving towards implementing project-organised courses. In this paper we make the claim that there is a need for quality criteria for project work, given that research provides a mixed picture of what students can potentially learn in project work. The empirical data in this case study consists of ethnography, video-recordings, video-diaries and interviews, from one project work with four students taking a six weeks long course on machine elements. Our analysis shows that the students spend substantial amounts of time on activities with little or no value to their education, but that this is interspersed with very productive moments. In addition, our analysis showed that two of the students worked considerably less than the other two, but the assessment structure made this more or less invisible to the teacher. The analysis also illustrates the uneven nature of implementations of group work and we argue that as engineering educators we must implement approaches to project work that bring out and utilise the valuable

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parts, while actively suppressing less productive parts, thereby producing a shift towards being more 'effective'.

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INTRODUCTION

Many engineering departments across the world are moving towards implementing project-organised courses with the aim of improving team-working skills and learning outcomes [1] and to better prepare students for professional practice where engineers generally work in teams [2]. There is broad (but uneven) support for different forms of cooperative learning within engineering education [3]. However, a more detailed understanding of in situ situations in engineering education of how students learn engineering collaboratively is needed. This is particularly pertinent as professional team work differ from project work within education where the main objective (in educational setting) is learning. Indeed, if students take a 'professional approach', which is to divide the workload efficiently and have a very strong focus on the end product, this may inhibit learning outcomes [4]. The purpose of this paper is to explore project work in engineering education, in order to contribute to criteria for quality of project work in relation to learning.

1 PROJECT WORK IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION

Project work as well as problem-based learning (PBL) became a part of international educational trends at many engineering institutions during the 1990s [5]. Kolmos points out [5] that *teamwork* is an integrated part of the concept of project work and is characterised by a number of phases: start, problem analysis, delimitation, problem solution, reporting and implementation. These are characteristics that are similar to structures in professional engineering team work. According to Kolmos this organisation of learning is based on the idea of teaching and learning as an *active* process of cognition, in contrast to traditional forms of education where students acquire knowledge. Furthermore, it is assumed that project work will lead to the development of social capabilities, such as team working skills, which are described as essential for the contemporary engineer [6].

Evidence of the effectiveness of active learning is vague, partly because the difficulty of defining what is being studied [3]. Prince's review [3] of effectiveness of active learning shows the importance of student engagement and that a considerable amount of research support the core elements of active learning such as student activity in traditional lectures while self-directed learning has a slightly negative effect on academic achievement. According to Prince [3], the results of the effectiveness of PBL (as well as project work) may be misleading since the forms of PBL vary significantly. In addition, relevant learning outcomes are simply difficult to measure. A generally accepted finding is that project work and PBL produces positive student attitudes [3]. However, there is no significant improvement on student test scores when implementing long-term project-like learning situation, whereas the introduction of moments of student interactivity in traditional lectures is unambiguously supported by research [3].

So far reports of 'successful' implementations of particular setups of PBL and project work have dominated the field of engineering education research [7]. However, these reports usually have a focus on student attainment on a general level where a detailed understanding of in situ learning situations in the groups is neglected [8]. Kittleson and Southerland's qualitative study [4], which explored knowledge construction in a group of engineers, is an exception. They followed a group of six students taking the course Design of Complex Continuum Systems. A total of 20 lab sessions were video-recorded. The analysis focused on conceptual talk, which is talk that involves the underlying concepts for the task, and procedural talk, which is the mechanics of the task. Using an analytical framework based on Gee [9] they found that social factors such as status became prominent and, more noteworthy, that an *engineering discourse* that promoted efficiency rather than learning gained precedence, which made the group divide the work among them. They also noted, in line with previous research, that students involved in project-based work, even under the best conditions, tend to spend a great deal of time involved in the procedures and administration of the project, rather than the engineering content involved. To sum up, when students work together, a good end product does not necessarily mean that the students have had possibilities to learn [10], due to students' tendency to divide the work among themselves. In this paper we argue that a key to reaping the benefits of project work is to assure that the conditions for time spent on conceptual talk and procedural talk are optimised in order to not be subjugated by the engineering discourse of efficiency.

2 CONTEXT OF THE STUDY AND ANALYTICAL PROCESS

In this paper we present a case study of one project work. The project was part of a six week course within a Swedish three years long Engineering Mechanics Programme which involves the design, production, and operation of machinery. Empirical data was collected through systematic observations of lessons (14 h) and video-recordings (8 h) from this specific project work, complemented with video-diaries with the four participants (3*7 min/student) as well as individual interviews (45 min/student). The empirical material has been collected in accordance with the principles of informed consent and voluntary participation. The project instructions given to the students within this course were very open, focusing on constructing and building a four-bar linkage. Each participant was expected to spend 20 hour on the project although most of the other project teams in the class spent considerably more time. We have focused on a group of four students, Student A, Student B, Student C and Student D and we chose to focus on this particular group because of two reasons. First, since we did not intend to focus on hierarchal relationships in this study, we choose a group that consisted of four men with the same age and ethnicity, and was in that sense typical in its homogeneous construction. Secondly, the students in this group highlighted interesting shortcomings of their project work, and elaborated on how it could have been improved.

The analysis was carried out in three main steps. First, we created a descriptive overview of the ethnographic work and video diaries/interviews, with a focus on who was dis/engaged in which activities. Second, we traced the interviews looking for different narratives on a group-level with a focus on the students' individual attitudes [3] towards their learning process. Third, we made an analysis of our transcribed video-data where all four the students worked collaboratively together. Our analysis of the video-data was based on the premises that social action is always collectively achieved, that not only the person producing an action, but also that the other that are present are part of the accomplishment of a social action [11]. The main feature of

video research is its possibility to capture detailed aspects of the students' talk together with small details of bodily conduct, embodied competencies and context [12]. Aware of that we analysed the production of meaning [13] through talk, the bodily behaviour of participants in relation to the material environment. The material environment here became surprisingly dominant in the students' interaction, which we will elaborate on later in our results. We searched for face to face interaction containing conceptual talk and procedural talk [4] as a criteria for quality of project work.

3 RESULTS

Our analysis of the ethnographic data and the video-recordings revealed that a considerable amount of time during the six weeks was spent on relatively mundane tasks. The first week the students were told to form smaller groups and for this particular group it took a several days to do this (in contrast to other groups in the classroom). The group also had problems deciding what to do; they talked about building a damper to a longboard or a clock for a few days, but agreed on that these ideas would be too difficult to implement. In the end of the first week Student A prepared a suggestion that they should build a prototype of a metal cutter and no one disagreed. Typical for the meetings during the first two weeks was that although they decided to meet at a certain time several participants turned up late, sometimes as much as ninety minutes late without notice, which Student A described with some frustration in his video-diary. After that they met and worked with building the prototype at least five times (three of these occasions were video-recorded), but only once during these occasions did all four students participate. The execution of practical work was generally without clear conceptual or practical challenges, disarray of conceptual terms and/or focused on considerations of minor importance from an engineering perspective. Notable in the data was that the Students C and Student D, did not participate or turned up very late on several occasions excusing themselves with sickness, tiredness or simply lack of interest. Student A became the spokesperson for the group, communicating with their teacher. Student B was there all the time and also arranged a meeting with a teacher from another engineering program in order to learn how to operate a laser cutter they needed to use later in the process. Student B also helped other projects in the course, using his expertise in welding.

In the students' video-diaries and their final interviews all four students gave different nuances to the story of this particular project work. Student A described (without specifications) some of the other students in the group as lazy 'with low level of ambition', but overall he found the project enjoyable, especially the moment where the laser cutter caught fire by accident. He also mentioned the moment where they all four got together as 'surprising but sort of fun'. Student B described the project work in even more positive terms: 'it is so fun and you learn a lot'. Student C and Student D were more negative when they talked about the project. Student C only talked positively about the one week he did participate. Still, Student C claimed that they should have divided the work between them even more, having less meetings in person, because that would have been more effective, according to him. Student D said several times in the data set that their project was very simple, and that they should have aimed higher. Something he mentioned as positive was the laser cutter, which was 'user-friendly and nice', although, as far as we know, he did not participate when they used this machine. None of them could be specific about what they learnt in this project, such as a scientific concept or deepened mathematical skills, although they were specifically asked to elaborate on this in the video-diaries and the interviews. When Student A was asked if they had calculated anything during the construction of the

metal cutter prototype he answered ‘No, not really. Rather... I guess we have used logical thinking’.

Nevertheless, on a closer look in our video data we found clear examples of episodes where the students engaged in focused valuable interchanges. We present an example here from the one time when they all four worked together, which Student A referred to as ‘sort of fun’. In the video they sit in front of a computer screen working with a draft copy of the prototype of the metal cutter in a computer program:

- 1 A:** The handle cover the knife and this link is on, is on [**Fig. 1**]
- 2 B:** this is much easier to see on your mobile or in the workshop hall [Student A holds his mobile phone in front of the screen so they all can see it]
[...Off-topic talk about if Student A is funny or not...]
- 3 C:** you can see it much better there, right [Student C refers to the picture on the phone]
- 4 A:** the blades are the same
- 5 C:** I didn't think of that, more like, on this, how the blade is oriented in comparison [**Fig. 2**],
- 6 A:** OK, I was thinking of this [**Fig. 3**] if you start from here, if you start, it becomes, loop-sided. [Student A illustrates with hand gestures that he refers to vertical forces]

Fig. 1. Student A refers to their draft copy on the screen in contrast to a real metal cutter.

Fig. 2. Student C points at one of differences between their draft copy and the metal cutter in the workshop hall.

Fig. 3. Student A explains that he is interested in vertical forces by turning the draft copy around.

At a first glance this could be interpreted as that the students plainly pointing at different models without purpose or goal, but when analysing with a focus on how content is presented this transcript contains how Student A points out relevant vertical forces in their draft copy of the prototype in contrast to a real metal cutter (1), and he worries that their draft copy might be skewed (6). In other words, they work with a quite an advanced engineering problem: to use two different models, their own ‘drawing’ and a metal cutter in the workshop hall, and merge them into a prototype that will preferably not be lopsided. In order to do this they use several different pictures: their model which they can turn around, a picture from an ad and their own photographs on Student A’s mobile phone. The conversation continues:

- 7 C:** this part goes down and this goes out, right, and this goes to the other side of the blade, haven't you seen that. [Student A points at the screen]
- 8 A:** eh... it has two drop arms, the original [**Fig. 4**], because then it is like...
- 9 C:** ...that's not what I meant, either
- 10 A:** but you meant down here [**Fig. 5**], it should only be...
- 11 C:** it has two that have contact with the opening, it works completely

differently, so the forces go, it is fracking two-dimensional

12 A: exactly, it is a fork [Fig. 6], it is more like a

13 B: what do you mean with fork?

14 A: that it cuts like scissors between [Student A points at his mobile phone]

15 B: between two like that

16 A: yes, exactly, and the blade goes down in the middle, that is how it is made, here, you can even see here [Student A points at the screen]

17 B: yes, that was what I meant, it goes down from the side like that

Fig. 4. Student A tries to explain what the real metal cutter looks like by pointing at the draft copy.

Fig. 5. Student A tries to verify if Student C referred to the bottom part of the real metal cutter.

Fig. 6. Student A illustrate what he means with the word 'fork' by making a fork with his fingers.

In the beginning of this transcript Student C points out (again) that one of differences between their draft copy and the metal cutter is that the blade is situated differently in the picture of a real metal cutter (7). Then Student A and Student C start to struggle with understanding each other's description of the real metal cutter, and Student A tries to explain his understanding by pointing at their draft copy from different angles (8-11). When Student A introduce the word 'fork' (12) to describe the differences between the two models they can finally agree on how the forces work in the real metal cutter in order to refine their own draft copy to get the same capacity. Here several content- and task-specific concepts and themes were in play (although not explicitly articulated in words). The students showed tacit knowledge of geometrical understanding as well as skills of handling a problem in two and three dimensions. This discussion continued for one hour and among other things they discussed size and choice of material as they considered function, stability, the process of production, and aesthetics.

In summary, this case study illustrates a diversity that exists within the same project work. Most of the students' time spent in this project work comprised into mundane tasks where two students showed tendencies of skulking. However, as we illustrated above, all four students had a discussion that satisfied our criteria for quality of project work in that the students were using underlying concepts for the task in their conversation [4]. Despite occasional use of swearwords, the students also created an atmosphere where everyone contributed to the discussion where the students showed their capability to draw on their engineering knowledge for disciplinary relevant considerations, and negotiate on what is appropriate and understandable for them, individually and as a group.

4 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Although it was easy for us (being there and having access to the video-data) to recognise the physical and cognitive absence of Student C and Student D, this may have been difficult for the teacher – both these students positioned the group as low-achieving and thus gave the impression of themselves as aiming for much more. The

video data also revealed other aspects of project work and learning possibilities than the interviews, partly because the students were not capable to articulate their learning processes. A variety of empirical data and a detailed understanding of in situ learning situations is necessary to capture the complexity of project work. In the engineering profession knowledge production balance on the border between the conceptual and practical, and often as in this situation encapsulated in project accomplishments. It is thus something inherently difficult to be articulated about and not necessarily readily recognisable for teachers, students, or researchers.

The conclusion points to the uneven nature of implementations of group work, and thus a mixed picture of what the students may learn. The students illustrated a capability to draw on their engineering knowledge, but their skills in articulating this knowledge was at the same time on a low level. This indicate that they would benefit from more practice in talking about underlying concepts related to the task in an engineering context [14]. There are prominent examples of moments where the group put their knowledge into action and develop their collaborative capabilities, which stretches their repertoire of possible expressions of engineering knowledge. This is consistent with much published research on group work, which often includes insightful moments from group discussions in specific groups [7]. Our results show that quite a lot of the time spent is on activities that are more or less pointless for their education, and that this co-exists with very productive moments. Thus, value of implementing group work has a value in and of itself must be questioned, which is in line with that research on more general implementation of group work seldom shows consistently good results [3]. As engineering educators we must implement approaches to project work that bring out and utilise the valuable parts, while actively suppressing less productive parts, thereby producing a shift towards being more 'effective'. Thus, it may be argued that the implementation of group work is not a search for the ultimate solution, but a question of systematically being able to identify and enhance the parts that presents a potential for quality learning, while removing or suppressing the parts which does not contribute very much to the students' learning process.

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